

DOI:

ABSTRACT

Electronic Resources are those resources whose deals with digital and digitized materials which can be either accessible from libraries in house database or from World Wide Web, the born digital materials includes e-books, e-journals, e-magazines, e-news papers, e-thesis etc. and other related materials which can be considered necessary by the user, researcher, informational professional, or even by the library management itself. The degree of acceptance and pattern of use of such materials is a great interest to library collection development. It is important that the library has an informed perspective on how E-Resources are used and valued by the user community regarding their awareness and use of these electronic materials. The objectives of the study were to determine users knowledge of e-resources; and purpose of use of e-resources, both number and frequency; and the areas of training needed. The questions covered computer literacy, computer access and location, knowledge and use of electronic resources, and training needs.

KEYWORDS: E-Resources, Electronic Resources, User study, Survey,

INTRODUCTION

The utilization of information and communication technology has become an indicator of the level a nation's wealth. The libraries are switching over to ICT based resources and services at an accelerated pace. E – Journals, e- Books, CD-ROM databases, online databases, web based resources and a variety of other electronic resources are fast replacing the traditional resources of libraries. IT is generally defined as the technology that deals with the collection, storage, processing, dissemination and use of information.

Academic libraries have been early adopters of electronic resources to provide information and services. They need not come physically to the library to use print formats but can stay at their place and access online library resources and services via networks or authentication methods at any time. Users often prefer increased access to databases of online refereed journals and to the Web which provides information that is up to the minute, international in scope, and sometimes not available elsewhere because they see these resources as easier to access and search. Availability of e-resources has changed what users actually read and use. They now tend to use only what is easily accessible. Therefore, they visit the library a lot less, and, as such, discovery through serendipity is reduced. Access to e-resources has decreased the time spent searching for information. The library plays a leading role in user relationships and in instructional services such as orientation and training in use of library resources. If efficient and effective use is to be made of library's e-resources, then user training will have to increase in both intensity and coverage. It is important that the library has an informed perspective on how e-journals are used and valued by the user community regarding their awareness and use of these materials.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Over the past few years, people's preferences for print and electronic resources have been the focus of numerous studies. Most of these studies were conducted in the academic environment, with particular attention given to surveying students and faculty.

Torma and Vakkari (2004) demonstrated relations between digital library use by university faculty, users' discipline and the availability of key resources in the Finnish National Electronic Library (FinELib), by using nationwide representative survey data. The results showed that the perceived availability was a stronger predictor of the frequency of use of its services than user's discipline. Regardless of discipline, a good perceived provision of central resources led to a more frequent use of FinELib. Similar study from Atilgan and Bayram (2006) reported the results of a survey on the use of e-databases at Ankara University. They surveyed faculty in 2002 to determine the level of awareness of digital library resources, particularly journal articles, along with their usage rate, and to evaluate the preferences of faculty for specific electronic databases. They distributed a questionnaire to researchers at Ankara University. The main findings were that the majority of respondents indicated that they knew that digital library resources available in Ankara University. Many of the faculty members (88 percent) used electronic databases.

Kurata, et al. (2007) in their study was carried out to show the position of electronic journals in scholarly communication based on Japanese researchers' information behavior and estimation. The survey method was questionnaire. The results showed that Japanese researchers used electronic journals as a matter of course, and other electronic resources to some extent, for accessing information; but that shift to electronic resources seemed to be not a transformation but a modification of traditional patterns of use.

Gowda and Shivalingaiah (2009) gathered data from researchers of humanities, social science and science disciplines in six universities in Karnataka. Results of the survey shows that in general research scholars prefer print resources and there exist significant differences in the preference of print and e-resources among various disciplines. The discipline wise responses show that the science researchers use the facility most and their counterparts in humanities use least. More than half of the social science disciplines respondents are using the facilities. Full text databases and e-journals are most used resources followed by bibliographic databases and portals.

Another study conducted by Kumbar and Gururaj (2009) indicates that electronic sources of information are highly useful for the research, teaching and learning processes. In order to make it successful and best use of the consortium, authorities of the University Library should conduct regular user education or awareness programmes to maximize the use of electronic sources of information more effectively and efficiently.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the study were

- (i) to identify the frequency of e-resources;
- (ii) to know the preferred type of e-resources,
- (iii) to know the availability of e-resources in their subjects,
- (iv) to find out the satisfaction level of the e-resources,
- (v) the areas of training needed by faculty to utilize e-resources efficiently and effectively and to recommend how the library could fulfill identified training needs;
- (vi) what strategies the library could use to improve service as well as what areas the library could research further.

METHOD OF STUDY

Questionnaire method was used to collect the data for the present study. The questionnaire comprised twenty-nine questions in three sections: (1) access to internet; (2) knowledge and use of electronic resources; (3) training. A Questionnaire was distributed to 150 users of different disciplines. Out of these 130 responded and the response rate is 86.7%. The data were presented in following tables.

Analysis and Interpretation

The data collected through questionnaires, observation and interviews were organized and tabulated, descriptive statistics were employed using SPSS for windows.

Table 1: Frequency of use Vs. Respondents

S.No.	Frequency of Use	Respondents
1.	At least Daily	51(61.9)
2.	2 or 3 times a week	32 (63.1)
3.	Once a week	39 (30.0)
4.	Rarely	8 (06.0)

The frequency of access to internet and average time spend on month has been shown in Table 1 and Fig.1. Majority of users were access the internet on 2-3 times in a week followed by daily. There are hardly users who access the internet on rarely basis. It seems that 95% of the respondents were using internet on regular basis.

Fig.1 Frequency of use

Table 2: Preferred type of E-Resources

S.No.	Preferred type of e-resources	Respondents
1.	E-articles/E-Journals	38 (29.20)
2.	E-books	26(20.00)
3.	E-Newspaper	35(26.90)
4.	Others	31(23.80)

Preferred type of E-Resources has been identified and shown in Table 2. A result shows that 29.20% of the respondents have preferred electronic journal articles; it is followed by e-newspaper. Only 20% of users were using E-books.

Fig.2 Preferred type of E-Resources

Table 3: Availability of E-Resources

It is important to know the adequacy of the available e-resources in the library and to find out to what extent the users feel about the collections.

S.No.	Availability of E-Resources	Respondents
1.	Available	112 (86.15)
2.	Not Available	18 (13.85)

Table 3 shows the availability of the e-resources in their subjects provided by the library. Most of the respondents are said that E-resources in the library is covered their subject and their requirements. Few Respondents complain that the e-resources are not covered their subject and internet speed.

Fig 3. Availability of E-Resources

Table 4: Satisfaction on E-Resources

S.No.	Satisfaction on E-Resources	Respondents
1.	Satisfied	105 (80.77)

2.	Not Satisfied	25 (19.23)
----	---------------	------------

Table 4 and Fig.4 shows the satisfaction of the user with the services provided in the library. Majority (80%) of the respondents are satisfied with available E-resources in the library. Only 20% of the Respondents complain that the e-resources are not covered their subject and internet speed.

Fig.4 Satisfaction on E-Resources

Table 5: Training on E-Resources

S.No.	Training on E-Resources	Respondents
1.	Short Time Training programmes are required	39 (44.82)
2.	Awareness Programmes need to be organized	36 (40.90)
3.	Existing library staff must be trained to provide timely assistance	16 (23.18)
4.	Latest information on e-journals must be promptly informed	39 (45.34)

The study attempted to know about the training required for maximum using of e-resources. Most of the respondents required Short time training programmes and awareness programmes for using e-resources. They said that latest update on e-journals should be informed promptly and library staff should give their assistance.

Suggestions

Based on the findings of the study, the following suggestions are put forward to improve the use of E-resources.

- More high end computers with high speed internet should be provided
- Some hand on training, orientation programs should be organized frequently by the library
- E-Resources facility should be made familiar to all.

CONCLUSIONS

The emergence of internet as a ubiquitous global information and communication resource propelled people's lives into the digital epoch. With the development of the internet and new information technologies, more and more of the educational resources are being produced, distributed and accessed in digital form. The Electronic Resources in the

virtual world represent a large investment of people's efforts and wisdom. E-resources at academic institution is important means and tools to support teaching, learning, and research. The study result shows that the usage of e-resources has great impact on higher education. As the number of e-resources available is good and satisfied the information needs. In spite of positive attitudes towards e-resources, there are some frustrations regarding their use. Lack of computer knowledge, doesn't know how to use and restricted access by publishers.

REFERENCES

- [1] Cochenour D and Moothart T (2003) 'E-journal Acceptance at Colorado State University: A Case Study' *Serials Review*, Vol. 29 pp. 16-25
- [2] Torma S. and Vakkari P. (2004) 'Discipline, availability of electronic resources and the use of Finnish National Electronic Library – FinELib' *Information Research*, Vol.10 No.1
- [3] Atilgan D. and Bayram O. (2006) 'An evaluation of faculty use of the digital library at Ankara University, Turkey' *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, Vol.32, pp.86-93
- [4] Kurata K. Matsubayashi M, Mine S, Muranushi T. and Ueda S. (2007) 'Electronic journals and their unbundled functions in scholarly communications: views and utilization by scientific, technological and medical researchers in Japan' *Information Processing and Management*, Vol.43 No.5 pp.1402-1415
- [5] Gowda V. and Shivalingaiah D. (2009) 'Attitude of research scholars towards usage of electronic information resources: a survey of university libraries in Karnataka' *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, Vol.56 pp.184-191
- [6] Kumbar B.D. and Gururaj S.H. (2009) 'Use of UGC-INFONET E-journals Consortium by Faculty members and Research Scholars of Karnataka University, Dharwad: A Study' *SRELS Journal of Information Management*, Vol.46 No.1 pp.61- 72
- [7] Kalsum, U. (2008). *Information communication Technology in Education*. Agra H.P. Bhargave Book House, 45-52.
- [8] Kirkup, Gill & Kirkwood, Adrian.(2005).*Information and communication technologies (ICT) in Higher Education teaching – a tale of gradualism rather than revolution*. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 30(2), 185-199.
- [9] Odufuwa, S. (2006). *Information and Communication Technology (ICT) as a research Tool in libraries*. *Nigerbiblios*. 17(1), 12-19.